

H2020 EINFRA-5-2015

www.bioexcel.eu

Project Number 675728

D1.2 – First project release of all pilot applications

WP1: Software Scalability & Usability

Copyright© 2015-2018 The partners of the BioExcel Consortium

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Document Information

Deliverable Number	D1.2
Deliverable Name	First project release of all pilot applications
Due Date	2017-03-31 (PM17)
Deliverable Lead	KTH
Authors	Mark Abraham (KTH), Emiliano Ippoliti (FSJ), Alexandre Bonvin (UU), Bert de Groot (MPG), Stian Soiland-Reyes (UMAN)
Keywords	Software Release
WP	WP1
Nature	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Final Version Date	2017-04-30
Reviewed by	PMB
MGT Board Approval	2017-04-30

Document History

Partner	Date	Comments	Version
KTH	2017-04-11	First draft	0.1
All WP1	2017-04-18	Second draft	0.2
FZJ	2017-04-24	Minor edits	0.3
KTH	2017-04-25	Accepted minor edits, submitted to PMB	0.4
KTH	2017-04-26	Updates	0.5
UNIMAN	2017-04-27	Clarify project releases	0.5.1
KTH	2017-04-28	Clarify code goals, contributions	0.6
KTH	2017-04-29	Implemented feedback from PMB	0.7
KTH	2017-04-29	Updates	0.8
UU,FZJ	2017-04-29	Updates	0.9
KTH	2017-04-30	Merges, spelling, attributed SS-R author	0.10
KTH	2017-04-30	Final version	0.11

Executive Summary

This document describes the contents of the first project release of software developed for pilot applications in BioExcel. The efforts of Work Package 1 are spread over the entire project timeframe, and some collaborations, deployments or benchmarks might also use preliminary new code. However, to establish known benchmark baselines and provide reference versions of all codes used in the project (e.g. to integrate them in BioExcel workflows and use by other BioExcel teams), the Work Package also makes these formal code releases. This also comes with records describing the current status of the software that results from the planning, development, documentation, and testing processes described in Deliverable 1.1. The release itself takes the form of a package of Open Source-licensed source code, and can be downloaded from the BioExcel webpage at <http://bioexcel.eu/software/code-repositories>. For most of the codes this is a BioExcel-specific repository to sync the releases with other project needs, while general users are usually recommended to follow the documentation, download and installation instructions available on the normal application web pages.

Contents

<u>1</u>	<u>INTRODUCTION</u>	<u>6</u>
<u>2</u>	<u>GROMACS</u>	<u>8</u>
<u>3</u>	<u>HADDOCK</u>	<u>12</u>
<u>4</u>	<u>QM/MM IN CPMD</u>	<u>14</u>
<u>5</u>	<u>CONTRIBUTIONS TO OTHER SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT</u>	<u>15</u>
<u>6</u>	<u>CONCLUDING REMARKS</u>	<u>15</u>

1 Introduction

All BioExcel pilot codes have been selected based on their external impact and active larger user communities, and because of this there is continuous active development both inside and outside of BioExcel. However, to synchronize work in the BioExcel project and provide well-defined baseline versions that can be used to integrate the pilot applications in workflows and benchmarking, BioExcel also provides public periodic project releases of the source codes, of which this is the first. The periodic releases will additionally enable stakeholders including both the European Commission, compute centers, and members of the bio-molecular simulation community to monitor the development going on in the project and provide valuable feedback to BioExcel.

Work package 1 covers “Software Scalability and Usability”, and the software efforts invested in BioExcel have been focused on providing added value in these areas, both by writing new code where necessary and by integrating, testing, maintaining and disseminating other contributions to the codes. Presently, the work covers three pilot codes:

- GROMACS, a high-performance molecular dynamics software simulation and analysis suite. GROMACS is one of the most widely used biomolecular simulation codes in PRACE, and the BioExcel work concerns scaling and performance improvements, as well as implementing modern techniques for modularization, documentation, code review and QA testing.
- Related to GROMACS, BioExcel also supports the PMX project for automatically preparing molecular topologies for advanced free energy calculations, which is a particularly important target for using massive amounts of molecular simulations both in academia and industry.
- HADDOCK, an implementation of bio-molecular docking based on a wide range of biochemical information. This code has a very different usage profile, and it has been selected because of the importance of improving support for high-throughput life science calculations. HADDOCK is a key component of the many workflows developed in BioExcel. Its main mode of use is via its web portal.
- CPMD, a high-performance plane-wave/pseudopotential implementation of density functional theory suited for *ab initio* molecular dynamics. This represents our third type of application work, where the BioExcel pilot efforts are focused on implementing libraries to make it possible to integrate different types of simulation codes for multiscale modeling.

In addition to software development focused directly on the applications themselves, another important part of the usability improvements in BioExcel comes from integrating them into workflows as presented in work package 2.

The BioExcel codes have very different degrees of parallelization maturity. They were selected to cover a range of proven-impact applications that face very different challenges when preparing for Exascale, but also to make sure the BioExcel project develops competence covering the entire scale of biomolecular modeling used in academia and industry today, ranging from QM/MM models on the small atomic scale to simulations of very large systems and rapid integrative

modeling. The modifications implemented in the pilot codes, interoperability libraries, and related workflows will facilitate using combinations of codes to solve application problems, but BioExcel does not aim to merge codebases. Apart from different user communities and licenses, there are fundamentally orthogonal development cultures and language standards, so we believe such efforts would rather end up with end users feeling a combination would complicate their day-to-day work (since it would need to cover a much broader area and different types of execution), while it would slow down development substantially. It should be acknowledged that an alternative approach could be to try and design a new grand unified “biomolecular” codebase from scratch, but in our experience previous such efforts have always failed. Our strategy is therefore rather to focus our efforts on improving proven-impact codes that scientists already want to use, while working to facilitate interoperability in general.

The contents of this release reflect the current status of the major ongoing effort of this work package on the pilot codes. This naturally encompasses the results of end-user consultation, team planning, software development, documentation, quality assurance, testing, and bug fixing that is expected for the output of a software e-infrastructure like BioExcel. The software development procedures were documented in Deliverable 1.1.

The project release is available from <http://bioexcel.eu/software/code-repositories> as a packaged source code archive for each of the three codes, as well as a convenience aggregate package (ALL_CODES). Many of the codes also provide extensive support and documentation through their existing web pages.

Although these BioExcel releases capture the improvements from BioExcel’s effort, those changes have also been contributed back to each upstream project’s code repository. Formally each pilot code’s community manages their own formal releases separately and at different intervals. This is in line with the expectations of their existing user bases and different needs for release cycles, as the codes are developed by particular research groups and institutions supported by multiple streams of funding. However, for some of the codes (GROMACS, HADDOCK) BioExcel staff are co-responsible for the main management and steering of the software development.

The valuable support of BioExcel is acknowledged by each upstream project, and as detailed in Deliverable 1.1, we have worked with them to harmonize software development practices, as well as clarify software licenses where appropriate. BioExcel has also had major impact on teaching and tutorials, including both user- and developer-focused activities to improve software quality. Valuable feedback and input into the requirements gathering process are also collected via BioExcel and thus the CoE helps defining future priorities for the individual developer communities.

BioExcel is committed to business-friendly open source licensing for all code developed in the project, but to ensure impact for the most widely used application codes we also need to ensure the code can be used with existing code bases and their licenses. This is handled by making all BioExcel code available as

independent libraries or scripts, which can easily be adapted to other codes too when more liberal licenses are available. The licenses used in BioExcel are the [Lesser GNU General Public License \(LGPL\) v2.1](#) (GROMACS and CPMD QM/MM), [LGPL v3](#) (pmx) and the [Apache License 2.0](#) (HADDOCK scripts). These are all [OSI-approved](#) and well-recognized Open Source licenses that grant the right to run the code for any purpose, to link it into closed commercial applications, as well as to modify and/or redistribute the code. The licenses differ mainly in minor details such as restrictions on derived works or protections against software patent infringements. We are currently working in collaboration with the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI, <https://www.software.ac.uk>) to detail the license implications for BioExcel users.

2 GROMACS

In BioExcel, GROMACS represents an advanced explicitly parallel code with multiple layers of parallelism (MPI, Pthreads/OpenMP, SIMD, CUDA/OpenCL). While the code can scale extremely well for sufficiently large systems, the BioExcel efforts are used to improve performance and scaling for typical medium-size systems used in scientific applications. BioExcel has also made it possible to invest significant efforts into introducing modern professional code development, testing practices, and better integration and testing of contributions from external users.

Over the last two years, the GROMACS project has moved from ad hoc feature-based releases that occasionally were up to a year late to enforcing a new policy of making annual source-code releases where features need to meet release deadlines. This follows a procedure starting around March each year, using internal alpha and public beta testing that leads to a release mid-summer. This has been very successful, and put an end to slipping releases.

To avoid users by mistake running program versions that were installed several years ago, GROMACS has changed the versioning scheme so each new major version number is the year of the new stable release branch (e.g. 2016). Each such branch is actively supported for two years by incrementing the minor version number – at any point in time there are both “stable” and “very stable” release branches available for users. The development branch is also publicly available, and guaranteed to pass all existing unit tests.

The main GROMACS project is managed by staff supported by BioExcel. The first major release that incorporated source code supported by BioExcel took place already in 2016. Every 2-3 months a routine bug-fix update is made, so in addition to the 2016 major release, official versions 2016.1, 2016.2 and 2016.3 have all incorporated major contributions from developers supported by BioExcel, as well as that from numerous other members of the global GROMACS development team. These releases have been advertised through the BioExcel channels, including the newsletter, webpage, and Twitter feed.

The first BioExcel project release version was coordinated with the internal deadlines for version 2016.3 (released to the public on 14 March 2017, according

to the versioning scheme described above), so benchmarks and workflow integration work will be done with a version that corresponds directly to a normal public stable release branch version. Considerable amounts of BioExcel-supported work will follow in the 2017 and 2018 releases, and some of this is currently awaiting review in the GROMACS code-review system (<https://gerrit.gromacs.org>). Following long-standing practice in the GROMACS project, all code is released under the *Lesser GNU General Public License, version 2.1 (or later)*, which permits unrestricted (including commercial) linking to the library as well as free or commercial modification or redistribution.

In addition to scaling and performance advances, much of the BioExcel work has focused on improving usability and sustainability of the code by providing better user and developer documentation as well as testing. The formal release process has been extended with support for automated construction and testing of both the source-code tar package and documentation. Documentation for the latest version is available at <http://manual.gromacs.org/documentation/>.

In particular, to avoid the constant issues of outdated documentation, all documentation is now generated automatically from in-code source. This documentation takes the form of terminal output returned by e.g. “*gmx help select*” or “*gmx select -h*”, which has content identical to “*man gmx-select*” and to that found on the version-specific webpages similarly generated automatically (e.g. see <http://manual.gromacs.org/documentation/2016.3/onlinehelp/gmx-select.html>). A Sphinx-based user guide, install guide, and release notes are also built based on the source code, along with more than 250 pages in the reference PDF manual, and the developer guide from a mixture of Sphinx and Doxygen. All these can be found online at <http://manual.gromacs.org/documentation/> and is also included within the BioExcel project release of GROMACS. BioExcel has also made it possible to provide extensive installation documentation targeting both novice users and experts at compute centers, covering e.g. compiler and MPI library recommendations and specific instructions to create builds for accelerator hardware such as CUDA, OpenCL or Xeon Phi.

The formal release notes found above are focused on things clearly of interest to users, including features added, deprecated and removed, along with bugs fixed and improvements to documentation and portability. However, BioExcel has also enabled a great deal of work not visible to users in these notes, including

- Development and maintenance of an automated infrastructure for code review, dissemination and testing,
- expanding the unit test coverage,
- extensive deployment of memory and thread sanitization builds as part of continuous integration to catch bugs
- usability testing of alpha/beta releases,
- organization of developer meetings and hackathons,
- adding developer documentation, and
- refactoring code for maintainability and future extension.

Notable achievements in the 2016 release series (as of 2016.3) relevant to the BioExcel objectives include:

- Raising the compiler language requirement to C++11, to facilitate the conversion to a library in that dialect of C++, with better modularization and encapsulation.
- Adding support for Tesla Pascal-series of GPUs (in particular P100) which is now available in some of the fastest machines in Europe (Piz Daint at CSCS), and a key component of the pre-exascale computing landscape.
- Support for hardware locality (hwloc) library to take the layout of hardware threads, cores, sockets, NUMA domains and PCIe bus locations into account to automatically optimize parallelization.
- Implementation of a new portable C++ SIMD acceleration layer which enables us to rapidly implement acceleration for new architectures. This release includes new acceleration for Power8, ARM64, AVX512 (KNL).
- Improving performance and scaling for numerous simulation kernels running on GPUs (both NVIDIA and AMD) and CPUs (see Figure 1), and also multi-simulations and improved parallelism combining MPI with OpenMP in to improve free-energy and pull codes.
- Adding usability safeguards to prevent simulations likely to be invalid.
- Improvements of the continuous-integration testing infrastructure to guarantee that every commit in the development branch passes all unit tests on all major architectures.
- Expanding unit test coverage of source code, and integration with Debian and Fedora software testing projects to identify unit tests failing on rare hardware/compiler combinations.
- Adding new functionality for free-energy pulling and computational electrophysiology features.
- Making many minor enhancements and fixes to setup and analysis tools
- Making many fixes for corner cases of portability, particularly with little-used build configurations.
- Removing minor features no longer supported

In particular, BioExcel funded the majority of the work on new CPU and GPU acceleration, parallelism, and virtually all work on improving sustainability through unit tests, documentation, and continuous integration. For the remaining features, BioExcel staff has been responsible for coordinating development and doing code review and testing. The present release will be used for the next phase of BioExcel work on workflow integration, training, and use cases involving large-scale free energy calculation, while the efforts in work package 1 will focus on further improving scaling.

Highlight: In GROMACS 2016, numerous key kernels were accelerated to make good use of SIMD lanes found on modern CPUs. This is illustrated in Figure 1. Four different biomolecular workloads were run on a single socket of x86 Haswell, POWER8, and ARM64 processors. In each case, the total wall time per MD step is reported for each configuration and software version as well as fractions attributable to some particular components of the overall MD step. In particular, the GROMACS SIMD modular compatibility layer proved its value by permitting developers to support the POWER8 and ARM64 SIMD architectures in mere days of work, showing dramatic performance improvements from GROMACS 5.1 to 2016.

Figure 1 Performance improvements after GROMACS 5.1, for some kernels and exascale-relevant architectures for which SIMD support was added or improved. For details, see the main text.

The **pmx** package is available as an add-on set of scripts for GROMACS and recently also made available from a web interface at <http://pmx.mpibpc.mpg.de/>. The web support has been added with BioExcel effort, as acknowledged within the interface. This makes pmx functionality for carrying out mutation free energy calculations accessible to all GROMACS users, without need for additional software, hence taking one step further in the BioExcel goal of making biomolecular simulations accessible to non-developers. In addition, support for nucleic acid mutations has been recently added, as well as rudimentary support for arbitrary ligands, taking an important step towards free-energy supported lead compound optimization.

The pmx project is maintained at the third-party repository <https://github.com/dseeliger/pmx>, and while that currently have no versioned releases, we have included a verified snapshot (5fb5781) of pmx within this GROMACS deliverable.

3 HADDOCK

The BioExcel work on HADDOCK is focused on improving HPC performance and usability of the throughput-focused research in life science that traditionally has found it very difficult to exploit HPC. This type of work is highly dependent on advanced automation and workflows, and some of the key BioExcel challenges for HADDOCK are related to enabling the code to be used efficiently in workflows and diverse HPC/Cloud environments. The main and most commonly used mode of access to HADDOCK remains direct submission to its web portal, which exposes a XMLRPC API. BioExcel-supported work on HADDOCK has led to the development, maintenance and release of numerous pre- and post-processing scripts for setting up and analyzing its docking runs. These are currently found at <https://github.com/haddocking/haddock-tools>, and <https://github.com/haddocking/pdb-tools> in addition to the BioExcel release repository.

The current stable release of pdb-tools which includes BioExcel-related additions is v1.1.0 (6cc0757). The pdb-tools contains a variety of python utilities for the processing of PDB files which should be valuable to a large variety of applications. Their use is in particular described in various HADDOCK online tutorial (see D4.5 section 2.7.1).

The first release of the haddock-tools is v1.0.0 (756bcfe). This release includes a variety of script utilities for the setup of HADDOCK calculations. They concentrate on PDB files manipulations and restraints generation and validation. The scripts include functionality for

- Defining interaction restraints to be used during a run of HADDOCK
- Validating restraints before launching a HADDOCK run
- Finding inter-chain or inter-segment contacts
- Wrapping the molprobit utility, for predicting histidine residue protonation states
- Cleaning structure descriptions in PDB files
- Mutating one residue to another in a PDB file

- Extracting residue sequences from PDB files

These scripts are released under the Apache License 2.0, which permits free use by all.

HADDOCK is intended to be used via a web interface found at <http://milou.science.uu.nl/services/HADDOCK2.2/>, which is free to use for non-profit users upon registration. This is the most-used access mode to HADDOCK with over 9000 registered users to date, but it is possible for users to obtain a license for using the code locally too. The web portal however performs several pre- and post-processing steps that are not available in the local install. The current official release of the local code is version 2.2, which was defined as background in BioExcel and shared with all partners.

HADDOCK has a critical dependency upon the third-party software CNS (<http://cns-online.org/v1.3/>) for the core computational work, which effectively restricts HADDOCK to those licensed to use CNS (free for non-profit). As part of WP1 activities, BioExcel has explored the feasibility of working towards relaxing this restriction, e.g. by replacing CNS functionality with GROMACS. This is work that will continue, but based on the codes' significantly different profiles it is not trivially possible to replace one with the other. This will require substantial coding efforts in both packages that go beyond what is feasible in the first stage of BioExcel, but we will continue efforts to improve the interoperability of both codes. There are currently too many CNS features missing in GROMACS (to mention a few: Torsion angle dynamics, several types of NMR restraints, the powerful selection syntax of CNS and its scripting ability – all docking protocols in HADDOCK are defined at the script level). Our long-term goal, however, remains to be able to replace the CNS computational engine in some future release after the current project, but this will require a major coding effort on both sides, something which is clearly not covered by the current PM resources.

The main HADDOCK web server infrastructure is also being greatly improved through upgrading into a Flask framework as part of WP1. This ongoing infrastructure work is necessary for the long-term support of HADDOCK and the kind of innovation that it supports, but is not yet suitable for a release, particularly as it would be difficult for third parties to set up their own web server for HADDOCK (and no support could be offered for the operation of such a third party web server). We are also working on the development of an improved Python interface to HADDOCK via its XMLRPC API. This interface should allow any Python pipeline to remotely access HADDOCK methods exposed via its API. It is also aiming to extend usual features offered through the web server to tightly control the process. This interface will facilitate the integration of HADDOCK into workflows.

We intent to launch the new web server in parallel with the release of HADDOCK3.0 (hopefully late 2017), which will include many features that are currently only supported by the web server (e.g. validation of input restraints, automatic definition of histidine's protonation state). It will also provide direct support for cryo-EM restraints as described in our Structure 2015 publication

(G.C.P. van Zundert, A.S.J. Melquiond and A.M.J.J. Bonvin. [Integrative modeling of biomolecular complexes: HADDOCKing with Cryo-EM data](#). *Structure*. 23, 949-960 (2015)).

While version 2.2 of HADDOCK is the official current release of the software, we do have version 2.3 available which support cryo-EM restraints and an implementation of the Martini coarse grain model. This version is however only suited for local installation. It is provided to users who require those features, but is not the official distribution version since our policy is to keep the local version in line with the web portal version since the majority of our user base is only making use of the web portal and this simplifies support.

4 QM/MM in CPMD

MiMiC is the HPC-oriented QM/MM interface for CPMD supported by BioExcel. The BioExcel team has built up a network of collaborations to implement this interface. This includes Prof. U. Rothlisberger (EPFL, Lausanne), Dr. T. Laino and V. Weber (IBM Research Zurich), J. M. Hugaard Olsen (University of Southern Denmark, Odense) and Simone Meloni (University “La Sapienza”, Rome).

This deliverable contains the first release of the CPMD-MiMiC communication library, developed by FZJ under the auspices of BioExcel. This piece of modular infrastructure is designed to facilitate communication between arbitrary QM and MM packages. The intent is to establish the data interaction between the QM and MM packages and transfer all the needed data (coordinates, forces, constraints, etc). This is the fundamental component of MiMiC QM/MM interface that enables the multiple program multiple data (MPMD) approach adopted for QM/MM interface. The library is implemented in C++11 based on the MPI 2.0 functionality. The library routines are provided behind a C API so that a stable application binary interface (ABI) is possible and to facilitate calling from FORTRAN, C and C++ programs. This flexibility is intended to permit different pairs of codes to use a common infrastructure, which offers the best prospects for ongoing access to these kinds of QM/MM biomolecular simulations.

The initial deployment will be between CPMD and GROMACS. This release marks the completion of the development of the communication library, while the development of the part of QM/MM interface driving the CPMD code is continuously updated at

<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/dp11t0hd0q0kb9m/AAAWrkRd0GPTOEWWh4600Hkj0a>

and already in alpha testing. Following this, coupling to GROMACS is the remaining part for having the first minimal functioning QM/MM build to move to beta testing. We are planning to implement this coupling by July 2017 and continue testing and benchmark procedures immediately after.

Beyond enabling the possibility to couple CPMD with virtually any force field-based code with minimal code intervention, the MPMD approach will benefit from the state-of-the-art parallelization scheme of both the classical molecular

dynamics code (GROMACS) and CPMD itself. Therefore, the new QM/MM interface is expected to outperform the current GROMOS96-based QM/MM interface implemented in CPMD, which does not exploit the CPMD parallelization scheme in an efficient way.

In conclusion, the CPMD QM/MM interface has been coupled to CPMD and given the MM forces (using file sharing for the moment). It is already able to reproduce results obtained with the GROMOS96 QM/MM old version. As soon as it is coupled to the GROMACS program and optimized for high efficient scalability, user testing can be started with the user feedback being used to drive further development of the Bioexcel interface. That updated release will take place in month 36, at the end of the project.

This library is released under the Lesser GNU General Public license, version 2.1, the same as GROMACS.

5 Contributions to other software development

In future phases, BioExcel plans to extend its capacity and sustainability as an e-infrastructure, by adding support for more codes. It is already preparing to do so by making contributions to other free and open-source software of interest to biomolecular simulation scientists. In particular, we have provided assistance to

- RELION-GPU (<http://www2.mrc-lmb.cam.ac.uk/relion>). This is a new GPU-accelerated parallel version of the most popular program to do Bayesian-based refinement of 3D reconstructions of cryo-EM densities. This work was enabled by extensive knowledge transfer from the BioExcel team, combined with two developers funded by Stockholm university. This involved a wide range of software development methodologies, including coding for GPUs, multi-threading, testing and build systems. Since fall 2016, RELION-GPU has become the dominant code to perform 3D reconstruction in cryo-EM, and the scientific paper including BioExcel researchers is cited multiple times per week.
- DisVis (<https://github.com/haddocking/disvis>), a tool to visualize and quantify the accessible interaction space of restrained biomolecular complexes, by providing a support forum on the BioExcel Discourse server,
- PowerFit (<https://github.com/haddocking/powerfit>), a program to fit high-resolution atomic structures in cryo-EM densities, by providing a support form on the BioExcel Discourse server, and

6 Concluding remarks

The pilot codes have released the software developed with the support of BioExcel. All new modules have been released under free and open business-friendly licensing, as planned. Valued contributions have been made to other related biomolecular simulation software, some with very high impact. In all cases, additional large amounts of work are underway and will be included in the

next formal project release, and as intermediary informal releases. D1.3 presents the long term roadmap of the pilot codes.